

CULTURE OF MASS MEDIA USE

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Abstract: When using the Internet, it is necessary to ensure that young people adhere to cultural and ethical norms strengthen ideological immunity, and in particular, achieve perfect mastery of information security and Internet culture, which includes features such as posting, distributing, searching, and using information on the Internet.

Keywords: global information space, "digest", "unfiltered" reception of messages, social networks

If we take a closer look at the global information space, not all the information contained in it can be considered useful or useless. In particular, at the moment, there are sites on the Internet that promote easy ways to commit suicide, have pornographic content, as well as violent and evil computer games, which are contrary to our national values and have a high probability of having a direct negative impact on the education of the young generation. Of course, measures are being taken to prevent such negative factors in our country. However, today it is clear to all of us that the problem will not be solved by restricting the Internet or banning access to information.

- If we look at the state of use of Internet resources by our youth, it is observed that most of them are regular users of foreign social networks. The fact that young people, who do not know the difference between good and bad, accept any information spread over the Internet as truth makes one seriously worried...

- There is soul in your comments. Unfortunately, today most of our young people are more interested in the influence of foreign spiritual and cultural currents due to globalization. Disregard for human dignity, responsibility, and morals is clearly visible in the clothes, character, and behavior of some young people.

In our opinion, the value of a person should be determined by his orientation to morality. Indeed, today information is coming in so much and so fast that to "digest" it requires deep thinking and a broad worldview. Such examples can be given about some computer games, especially in today's era, when the Internet world is attracting the attention and interest of our children.

According to experts, 49 percent of computer games distributed over the Internet contain a significant amount of violence and evil, and 41 percent of violent games involve the hero of the game committing such violence and evil in order to achieve his goal. In 17 percent of games, this violence and evil itself is the main goal. Games like this, which are not compatible with our mentality and sometimes turn into heroic barbarism, undoubtedly have a negative impact on the moral and aesthetic education of young people. At first glance, they seem like a simple game, but real-life examples prove that ideas of violence, awakening the mood of evil, lead to many negative consequences. Ideological traps on the Internet are also dangerous because they seem like culture and appeal to young people like oil. In human morals, the negative mob culture is spreading dust in the minds of some young people and turning into a spiritual trap. Unfortunately, young people often do not realize that they are influenced by this "culture" or become its victims.

The minds of young people are being poisoned as a result of "unfiltered" reception of messages from the global information system. For example, young people who enter the site in order to get some necessary information, see a sensational announcement such as "such and such famous person has crashed" and unwittingly open it. In addition, there another site will open and read more scam messages. In this way, young people are caught in the trap of swindlers. A teenager exposed to such a disgusting "culture" will grow up to be a careless person, who

looks at life lightly, indifferent to the development of the country and the peace of the people.

The mass media, the Internet, including social networks and mobile messengers, should carry out continuous monitoring of information that has a negative impact on the opinion of the general population, and the information services of the relevant state bodies and organizations should respond to them. to be sent [3]. Today's great changes in our life, the logic of our reforms require everyone to work in a new way, to come up with new ideas and initiatives. In this sense, strengthening the material and technical base of the mass media, personnel capacity, achieving a worthy place for our national press in the international arena, developing internet journalism, wide introduction of market mechanisms in publishing, book sales, and subscription issues, establishing work in an environment of openness and healthy competition. We have to work hard on.

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